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**LibrarIN [101061516]: Value Co-creation and Social Innovation
for a new Generation of European Libraries**

**D6.2 Report on Dissemination and Communication
Activities v1.0**

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Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

LibrarIN, “Value co-creation and social innovation for a new generation of European Libraries”, is a Horizon Europe funded project that provides new avenues for participatory management and sustainable finance for European libraries as key cultural institutions. The main goal of LibrarIN is to discover, analyse and provide managerial and policy recommendations for transformative strategies that integrate the co-creation of value in public libraries. LibrarIN focuses its research on exploring the paradigm shift from the traditional top-down model of service design, to demand and bottom-up driven models, where citizens, civil servants, and private and third sector organizations voluntarily participate in the development of transformative social innovations that can address changing needs and solve social problems.

Apart from the critical work conducted at the level of LibrarIN research and policy Work Packages (WPs), another key Work Package (WP) of the project is WP6, concerning the dissemination, communication and sustainability of the project objectives, research results, policy recommendations, and expected impacts. Dissemination and communication are a critical part of LibrarIN, both in terms of reaching out to, raising awareness of and informing the general public, citizens etc. about the benefits of participatory models for public library services design and value co-creation, and also in terms of informing and mobilizing the research and policy communities to actively participate in the transformation of European libraries. This two-level communication approach is inherent to the rationale and goals of LibrarIN; for people to engage and participate meaningfully in creating public library services and public library innovations, they first need to be aware of these concepts and their expected benefits.

From the beginning of the project, a lot of weight was given to defining an appropriate dissemination and communication strategy. LibrarIN’s dissemination and communication strategy was created during Month 4 as part of the project’s Dissemination, Communication and Sustainability Plan (D6.1). The Plan contains a detailed description of the project’s strategy, communication and dissemination channels, tools and activities. LibrarIN follows a two-dimensional outreach model, with communication activities targeting a wider and not so specialized audience (citizens and generally people interested in LibrarIN’s thematic topics) and dissemination activities targeting more specialized audiences (researchers, policy makers, practitioners). Moreover, LibrarIN’s dissemination and communication strategy consists of three phases that run respectively from Year 1 to Year 3 of the project: a) the awareness-oriented phase, b) the result-oriented phase, and c) the sustainability & wider dissemination phase. The Plan also sets the project’s objectives in terms of the communication and dissemination impact and defines the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be monitored. The Dissemination, Communication and Sustainability Plan is used as a roadmap for all the activities that have been and will be performed until the project’s end. In this framework, the present deliverable aims to report and offer a first summary of all the dissemination and communication tools and activities that were deployed from the beginning of the project until Month 18.

Taking into consideration LibrarIN's two-dimensional outreach model, as well as the three phases of the dissemination and communication strategy, the first 12 months of the project were focused mainly on raising public awareness around the project through general communication activities, consistent with the awareness-oriented phase. The tools mostly used during this period were LibrarIN's X/Twitter and LinkedIn accounts and blog. The topics covered included general information about the project approach and objectives, as well as relevant news and developments in the fields of social innovation, co-creation, and libraries. At the same time, the project undertook several different dissemination activities, with project partners producing scientific publications and delivering project presentations at relevant conferences. LibrarIN's preconference workshop titled "Value Co-Creation and Social Innovation for a New Generation of European Libraries" was organised in the framework of LIBER's Annual Conference 2023, while LibrarIN's first in-person stakeholder panel meeting took place in Amsterdam.

Moving to the second dissemination and communication phase, the result-oriented phase, months 13 to 18 of the project were focused on promoting the first research results produced by the research WPs. The tools mostly used, during this phase were again LibrarIN's X/Twitter and LinkedIn accounts and the blog, with the difference that the range of topics covered, and the language used, were more specialized and designed to target LibrarIN's expert stakeholders and the research and policy community. At the same time, the webinar titled "Sustainable Models for GLAMs-New Ways of Participatory Management and Sustainable Financing of Cultural Institutions" proposed by the Cluster HERITAGE-01-02 projects, GLAMMONS, RECHARGE and LibrarIN, was organised.

In the next eighteen months of the project, our main activities will focus on disseminating the research results and policy recommendations. As we approach the end of the project, the amount of output will increase. We will also be interacting more with LibrarIN's stakeholders panel to obtain their feedback. This will ensure that the results and policy recommendations of LibrarIN are relevant and actionable.

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List of Terms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
ATC	Athens Technolocy Center S.A.
EU	European Union
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LC	The Lisbon Council
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
Q&A	Questions and Answers
RUK	Roskilde University
UAH	University of Alcalà
UKON	University of Konstanz
ULILLE	University of Lille
UM	Maastricht University
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

1 Introduction

LibrarIN aims to discover, analyse and provide managerial and policy recommendations for transformative strategies that integrate the co-creation of value in public libraries. This will be achieved by introducing a new model of public service and social innovation. The project intends to explore how to co-create value for individuals and society through the use of design thinking and co-creation/collaboration to design and deliver innovative library services. It will also identify models to resolve potential conflicts between individual values and social values. More specifically, LibrarIN aims to:

- Provide a comprehensive and holistic theoretical framework.
- Measure and monitor transformative innovation in public libraries.
- Focus on three areas of transformation within public service co-creation in libraries.
- Generate sustainable impact in library policy and practice.
- Set up an online tracker system for the benchmarking of library value co-creation.
- Exploit the achievements of LibrarIN through a sustainable research and innovation lighthouse.

In this context, WP6 aims to communicate and disseminate the activities and results of LibrarIN, in order to create awareness towards the scientific and policy community, various stakeholders, practitioners, and citizens, and hence to set the foundations for successfully delivering sustainable policy impact.

In this framework, a dissemination and communication strategy (D6.1 Dissemination, Communication & Sustainability Plan) appropriate for the nature and needs of the project was designed early on in the project's lifecycle. Based on this strategy, LibrarIN – over the first 18 months - has carried out traditional, large-scale dissemination and communication activities, through both online and offline channels.

As set out in the Deliverable "*D6.1 Dissemination, Communication & Sustainability Plan*", LibrarIN dissemination and communication strategy consists of three phases that run respectively from Year 1 to Year 3 of the project as depicted in Figure 1 below.

- The **awareness-oriented phase** aims at creating stakeholders 'awareness and raising public interest. During this phase, which has now been concluded, a dissemination, communication and sustainability plan was developed, a public website was created, a project identity kit was designed (including project branding, poster, templates for internal and external materials and guidelines for consortium partners), while introductory presentations at conferences and workshops to raise the awareness of the stakeholders were also organized. This phase coincides with the first year of the project.

- The **result-oriented phase** shall promote the results of the project to (potentially) interested parties (including the scientific audience). During this phase, which is now running, public deliverables and news are displayed on the project website for viewing and downloading in order to show the progress of the project and to keep the stakeholders updated. In addition, scientific publications are submitted to scientific journals and presentations are given at conferences and workshops. After completing important milestones, the consortium is publishing press releases, blog posts, and policy briefs. This phase runs through the second year of the project.
- **The sustainability & wider dissemination phase**, which will take effect at the beginning of Year 3, will deploy specific activities in order to ensure the sustainability of the project outcomes. To this end, a detailed sustainability plan will be developed to enable the transformation of LibrarIN into a sustainable think tank. During this phase, different revenue streams will be analysed, as well as presentations and pitches will take place to at least three potential private and public funders.

Figure 1: The three phases of LibrarIN dissemination and communication strategy

Deliverable "D6.2 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities v1.0" constitutes the first report on the project's dissemination and communication activities and its submission is placed at the middle of LibrarIN's lifecycle, as well as at the middle of phase two (result-oriented phase) of the dissemination and communication strategy.

During this period, dissemination and communication activities have been focused on two main goals. One was to concentrate on making the project known among its different target audiences as defined and categorised in "D6.1 Dissemination, Communication & Sustainability Plan" and to raise awareness

among potential stakeholders, particularly libraries, scientific and academic community and policy-makers, as well as Citizens and Students. The other goal was to bring together and reinforce links between different global communities of policy-makers and practitioners.

Making the project known was key to creating awareness for the project, getting people on board, and raising their interest in LibrarIN's work. During Year 1, communicating the project objectives, concepts, and expected results was a key task to achieve this. This was best done through channels like the project website, blog, X/Twitter and LinkedIn, which enabled us to spread information about LibrarIN and to connect with a wider audience of interested individuals and groups, but also through participation and project presentations in conferences and organisation of workshops.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The present deliverable describes the dissemination and communication activities that took place during the first 18 months of the project and outlines the planned activities for the remaining duration of the project. More specifically, the deliverable outlines the dissemination and communication objectives and strategy of the reporting period. It presents the tools and activities that were undertaken to accomplish the set objectives, disseminate the project, and implement the strategy as it was set out in the deliverable "*D6.1 Dissemination, Communication & Sustainability Plan*".

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

The present deliverable is comprised of eight (8) sections.

Section 1 serves as an introduction and presents an overview of the project and its objectives, the work included in WP6 regarding the dissemination and communication of the project, as well as the purpose and scope of the present deliverable. Section 2 gives a high-level overview of LibrarIN's dissemination and communication strategy and foreseen activities at a glance. Section 3 presents the dissemination and communication activities undertaken during the first 18 months of the project, including the project website and its impact, the social media activities, and scientific and non-scientific dissemination & communication activities. Section 4 presents the project materials that have been created and used for dissemination purposes.

In Section 5, the target values for the project period are compared against values achieved by considering the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in LibrarIN's Dissemination, Communication & Sustainability Plan (D6.1), in order to assess the progress so far. Section 6 provides an overview of the second dissemination and communication reporting period, describing future dissemination activities and indicative dissemination events and scientific journals/books that the project will target. Finally, Section 7 concludes this deliverable, while Section 8 contains supporting elements of the various dissemination and communication activities undertaken during the first 18 months of the project.

2 Strategic Dissemination and Communication Plan at a glance

This section presents a high-level overview of LibrarIN’s dissemination and communication activities to be undertaken throughout the whole duration of the project. During the first 18 months of the project, WP6 focused its efforts on developing and implementing the appropriate dissemination and communication strategy and activities that will result in the most effective promotion of the project at a national, European, and international level. This is achieved through the contributions of all project partners.

LibrarIN aims to make significant contributions to research and policy by producing instruments to reach different **target groups** involved in co-creation and transformative innovation in public libraries, as outlined below.

Primary group

- Libraries
- Scientific and academic community: researchers and (university) students
- Policy-makers

Secondary group

- Citizens –library end users
- Students

In order to target these different audiences and stakeholders in an efficient way, we have addressed the different audiences through the appropriate channels and messages presented in the following table.

Table 1: Approaching Target Groups

Target group	Tools	Main Directions for Messages
PRIMARY TARGET GROUP		
Libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • website • social media • newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness • attract • strengthen impact
Scientific and acad. community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • open access publications • conferences, conferences’ publications • special issues • workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness • attract • scientific dissemination
Policy-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • brochure • videos • knowledge management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policy making • strengthen impact
SECONDARY TARGET GROUP		
Citizens & General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • website • social media • traditional media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness • attract

For the first 18 months of the project, the main Dissemination & Communication objectives were the following:

- Build the LibrarIN brand name.
- Produce key project material.
- Disseminate project’s vision & objectives.
- Start engaging stakeholders.
- Leverage the participation of different stakeholders.
- Reach out to the wider community of non-experts.

The following figures (Figure 2, 3 and 4) present the dissemination and communication activities that were planned for Year 1, Year 2 and Year 3 respectively of the project. For Year 1, all the activities have been performed and concluded successfully.

Figure 2: Overview of dissemination and communication activities for Year 1

Regarding Year 2, it should be noted that this deliverable (D6.2) covers the first half of the second year and, as such, some of the activities presented in the following Figure 3 have been performed, while others are in progress.

Figure 3: Overview of dissemination and communication activities for Year 2

As for Year 3, the following dissemination and communication activities will be performed as planned.

Figure 4: Overview of dissemination and communication activities for Year 3

As seen in Figures 3 and 4, the next major activities for WP6 planned for the following eighteen months of the project (May 2024 –October 2025) are as follows:

- Keep publishing information about the project on the website and blog.
- Update the website.

- Use the power of social networks to engage LibrarIN's audience and share key project activities and results (X/Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube).
- Attend key events like conferences and deliver presentations of the project's results.
- Prepare scientific publications and articles.
- Engage with the stakeholders' panel and ensure they will provide relevant feedback.
- Publish 4 policy briefs and organize the respective policy events.
- Create and publish several press-releases; create and publish newsletters.
- Prepare presentations in traditional media such as TV, newspapers, radio, etc.
- Organise project Stakeholder Panel events.
- Create a promo video.
- Consolidate our cooperation with other relevant EU projects and Cluster projects.
- Establish contact with potential donors and funders and present them LibrarIN results.
- Organise LibrarIN international conference.

3 Dissemination & Communication activities

3.1 Project Website

In this section, we describe and report on the impact of the project website which is available under the domain <https://librarin.eu/>.

3.1.1 Website Overview

As the central node for dissemination purposes and the main dissemination and communication channel, the LibrarIN official website was built in the early stage of the project (17th January 2023). The website serves as a collaboration tool for knowledge, experience and best practice sharing, as well as for results consolidation and dissemination support. The project website is continuously maintained to provide up-to-date information and material on the project’s deliveries and news. Figure 5 below presents the website’s homepage.

Figure 5: LibrarIN website homepage

Apart from the standard webpages like the “About LibrarIN” and “Who we are”, we have also created a project repository (“Resources”), where visitors can browse and download all public deliverables of the project, project publications, as well as the project’s identity kit (logo, brand guide, brochure, poster). All the public deliverables created during the project's first year are uploaded on the LibrarIN website, so as to increase the dissemination of research produced within the consortium and make it publicly available to interested researchers and policy makers. To ensure long-term visibility and an efficient dissemination of the project results, a LibrarIN community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/librarin>) was also created. At the moment, all public deliverables can be found in this community.

Moreover, LibrarIN maintains an active blog, where we upload interesting posts about the project and its results, as well as about project events and other developments in the fields of social innovation, co-creation, and libraries. Figure 6 presents an example of one of our blog posts with the higher engagements. Having a blog is one of the most effective ways to attract visitors, spread project news effectively, and regularly update the site, which increases the website’s Search Engine Optimization and results in higher rankings.

Figure 6: Example of LibrarIN blog post

During January 2024, we have created the “[Stakeholders](#)” landing page under the “Who we are” section, where any interested party can find the members of the LibrarIN stakeholder panel (name, picture, short bio and motivation for joining the project are provided where applicable).

Figure 7: LibrarIN website – Stakeholders webpage

3.1.2 Website analytics

This section presents figures from the Google Analytics page of the LibrarIN website from the day of its creation to the time of drafting the present deliverable (21st April 2024). On aggregate, from the beginning until now, a total of 2,7K new users have visited the website, while the website has a total of 9,2K page views. Throughout the whole period that the website has been operating, we have had a stable number of monthly users, with increments appearing whenever there is an important project activity.

Figure 8: Overview of Google Analytics for the LibrarIN website

Regarding the geographical distribution of LibrarIN’s audience, it is interesting to note that LibrarIN has achieved a wide reach, with website visitors coming from almost all over the world and covering Africa, Asia, Australia, Europe, North America and South America continents (see Figure 9 below). The top five countries with the most visitors are Ireland, Netherlands, Spain, Greece and Austria, as depicted in Figure 10 below.

Figure 9: Overview of geographical distribution of LibrarIN website users

Country	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user	Average engagement time	Event count
	2,691 100% of total	2,690 100% of total	1,976 100% of total	39.27% Avg 0%	0.73 Avg 0%	1m 01s Avg 0%	23,661 100% of total
1 Ireland	1,568	1,568	93	5.9%	0.06	2s	4,997
2 Netherlands	127	124	205	43.52%	1.61	1m 42s	2,053
3 Spain	117	116	128	54.7%	1.09	1m 32s	1,254
4 Greece	91	91	467	56.61%	5.13	6m 22s	5,312
5 France	76	74	72	58.54%	0.95	1m 31s	726
6 Austria	75	73	78	53.42%	1.04	1m 18s	824
7 Italy	66	63	86	57.72%	1.30	2m 24s	829
8 Germany	65	63	68	61.26%	1.05	2m 25s	663
9 Belgium	57	48	53	55.21%	0.93	2m 22s	498
10 United Kingdom	42	40	37	54.41%	0.88	56s	310
11 Bulgaria	40	40	30	47.62%	0.75	1m 43s	350
12 Finland	32	31	27	48.21%	0.84	1m 00s	280
13 Denmark	31	28	28	63.64%	0.90	1m 41s	297
14 Hungary	26	24	24	58.54%	0.92	2m 23s	289
15 Sweden	26	25	30	46.88%	1.15	1m 20s	262
16 Poland	25	25	26	74.29%	1.04	2m 33s	202
17 Portugal	25	25	308	65.12%	12.32	10m 33s	2,102
18 Ukraine	24	25	39	23.21%	1.63	5m 56s	617
19 United States	24	24	15	41.67%	0.63	50s	171
20 Czechia	19	16	25	64.1%	1.32	37s	169
21 Norway	13	13	12	70.59%	0.92	1m 19s	103
22 Slovenia	13	11	14	45.16%	1.08	3m 36s	179
23 Switzerland	13	11	13	56.52%	1.00	58s	138
24 Canada	12	12	7	46.67%	0.58	28s	66
25 Australia	11	11	1	8.33%	0.09	4s	38

Figure 10: Top 25 countries with the most website users

Figure 11 below presents the top referral channels for the LibrarIN website. Most website traffic (above 2.1K users) is direct or comes from organic search. Direct traffic is defined as visits with no referring website. When a visitor follows a link from one website to another, the site of origin is considered the

referrer. These sites can be search engines, social media, blogs, or other websites that have links to other websites. Direct traffic categorizes visits that do not come from a referring URL, while organic search traffic is defined as traffic coming from search engine results that is earned, not paid. Following direct and organic search, the acquisition of users (around 340) comes from referrals (other websites) and social media. This is to be expected, as LibrarIN doesn't use paid search results or ads, while the percentage of referrals and social media is within the normal rates for a website such as LibrarIN (academic and scientific oriented content interesting for specific audiences that are not heavy social media users).

Figure 11: Top Channels for LibrarIN user acquisition

Finally, concerning the webpages that attract most of the website's users, Figure 12 below presents the list of the 10 most popular webpages within the LibrarIN website.

Page path and screen class	Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time	Event count All events	Key events All events
	9,190 100% of total	2,691 100% of total	3.42 Avg 0%	1m 01s Avg 0%	23,661 100% of total	0.00
1 /	2,899	883	3.28	53s	8,417	0.00
2 /about-librarin/overview/	562	292	1.92	59s	1,243	0.00
3 /who-we-are/partners/	557	356	1.56	30s	1,159	0.00
4 /blog/	458	122	3.75	56s	975	0.00
5 /resources/public-deliverables/	291	145	2.01	39s	620	0.00
6 /resources/material/	264	140	1.89	25s	556	0.00
7 /about-librarin/approach/	244	129	1.89	1m 06s	534	0.00
8 /about-librarin/results/	223	123	1.81	1m 09s	461	0.00
9 /stakeholders-panel/	199	39	5.10	1m 31s	411	0.00
10 /who-we-are/stakeholders/	156	63	2.48	1m 18s	374	0.00

Figure 12: List of most visited webpages

3.2 Social Media channels

Social media profiles play a pivotal role in the project to reach a wide range of audience. Constant posts and updates of status on social media profiles on the project's developments, news and sharing of best practices and research developments increase audience engagement and help to achieve interaction with the users. This is of particular importance to the project, as it is related to library services innovations, so the attraction of very specific audiences, like policy-makers, is vital. Social media proves to be most effective in dissemination and communication due to the popularity, ease of access and rapid information flow. The project social media profiles were created on X/Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, the link to LibrarIN's X/Twitter account was integrated into the project website, and an additional feed flow is being shown on the project website, inviting users to browse through the interesting topics posted on LibrarIN's X/Twitter.

3.2.1 X/Twitter

LibrarIN's X/Twitter channel (https://twitter.com/LibrarIN_eu) was the first communication channel that was created. It was used as one of the main digital distribution channels besides the project's website. With its open structure and the cross-linking feature via hashtags, the channel offers a very efficient way to reach out to different audiences and connect to people directly. Via X/Twitter it is also easy for our followers to engage with the project, either by following, mentioning, retweeting or commenting on our tweets. During the first half of the project, we used this channel both to promote blog posts on project's news and events and other content published on the website as well as to share exciting articles and links around the LibrarIN domain. Figure 13 shows the LibrarIN X/Twitter page.

Figure 13: LibrarIN X/Twitter page

Via X/Twitter Analytics the following data analysis for the LibrarIN X/Twitter channel has been gathered:

Table 2: LibrarIN X/Twitter Analytics (December 2022 – 21st April 2024)

Number of Tweets	174
Posts with retweets	262
Followers	105
Following	88
Retweets	209
Reach	24334
Likes	383
Link Clicks	262

To date we have posted 174 tweets and 262 posts with retweets. We have a follower base of 105 people, and we follow 88 people. A large part of this follower base is interested in what we have to say, which can be derived from the number of retweets (209) that are being retweeted. We have received 383 likes on our posts, and we have a total of 262 link clicks, indicating the relevance of what we have to say. All of this gives us a reach of 24.334 views.

Posts	Top posts	Posts and replies	Promoted	Impressions	Engagements	Engagement rate
	LibrarIN_eu @LibrarIN_eu · Jun 22	#BreakingNews 📣 Our project has an official LinkedIn page! Follow us to keep up with our progress 🙌 linkedin.com/company/librar... #librarin_eu #LinkedIn		618	32	5.2%
	@LIBEREurope @lisboncouncil @UAHes @roskildeuni @univ_lille @UniKonstanz @MaastrichtU @VTTFinland @AITtomorrow2day @iLabATC pic.twitter.com/7ZwHgFSbYj					
	LibrarIN_eu @LibrarIN_eu · Oct 6	📣 The 1st #librarin_eu Stakeholder Panel meeting is about to start. 25+ library stakeholders from all over Europe have joined the project members for a day, at the @VUamsterdam, to share their experiences and expertise, and co-create new library initiatives. pic.twitter.com/TvbB3iHgo8		605	93	15.4%
	LibrarIN_eu @LibrarIN_eu · Jun 2	📺 LIVE from @roskildeuni for the second day of our 2nd General Assembly Meeting - Barbara vd Vaart (@LIBEREurope) and Evgenia Malikova (@lisboncouncil) introduced the WP5 and the Stakeholders Panel, its composition and role. The Panel will support policy outcomes. #cocreation pic.twitter.com/V5kO6dcQ6o		560	52	9.3%
	LibrarIN_eu @LibrarIN_eu · Jun 1	📺 LIVE from the 2nd General Assembly Meeting of #librarin_eu, hosted by our partner @roskildeuni ! Today we are at the Danish Social Innovation Academy in #Copenhagen, discussing the project's progress so far & next steps! Stay tuned for more updates! pic.twitter.com/mHsQoBvHAR		512	28	5.5%
	LibrarIN_eu @LibrarIN_eu · Oct 4	📣 We are for three days at the @VUamsterdam for the 3rd General Assembly Meeting of #librarin_eu and the 1st Stakeholder Panel meeting, hosted by our partner @LIBEREurope. We will discuss the project's progress after a year, and plan the next steps! 📖 pic.twitter.com/ZRiW6addQs		511	42	8.2%
	View post activity					

Figure 14: LibrarIN X/Twitter - top 5 tweets since the beginning of the project

3.2.2 LinkedIn

Early in the project, LibrarIN utilised the already existing LinkedIn group “Public Sector Transformation” (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4165795/>) that the H2020 project [Co-VAL](#) maintained. The LinkedIn Group moderated by ATC and LC is a private one, numbering more than 3.700 members from the policy, research and public sector communities. The project tried to enhance the already created Community and used the group to announce LibrarIN achievements to other professionals from relevant fields of action. The logic behind this choice was that it was deemed more effective to build on and exploit this already established Community of 3.700+ users rather than start a new community from zero, which would consume more project resources and probably would never reach this number of users. The project will continue posting selected project’s results to this Community in order to increase visibility.

In June 2023, it was agreed among partners to create a LinkedIn page for the project (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/librarin-project>), as a channel to spread information about the project and reach well defined and relevant target audiences. The LinkedIn Page serves as the official representation of the project on LinkedIn. It offers a way to showcase the project information and updates to a professional audience while LinkedIn users can follow and engage with this page to stay informed about the latest developments and news from the project. It also portrays our project’s voice not individual voices as in a LinkedIn group. The page was regularly updated with posts on LibrarIN’s news and events, and other content published on the website as well as interesting articles and links about the project’s topics. This resulted in people staying informed about the activities of the project and bringing some referral traffic from LinkedIn to the project’s website. Figure 15 shows the LibrarIN LinkedIn page.

Figure 15: LibrarIN LinkedIn page

Via LinkedIn Analytics the following data analysis for the LibrarIN LinkedIn channel has been gathered:

Table 3: LibrarIN LinkedIn Analytics (June 2023 – 21st April 2024)

Number of Posts	80
Followers	190
Reach	14337
Shares	88
Likes	424
Clicks	723

Up to date we have posted 80 posts and we have a follower base of 190 people. The number of posts shared is 88 while 424 of our posts have been favoured (liked) and we have gained a total of 723 link clicks. All of this gives us a reach of 14.337 views.

3.2.3 YouTube Channel

The project has created a LibrarIN channel on YouTube (https://www.youtube.com/@LibrarIN_eu), with the goal to publish and promote the videos that will be created in the framework of the project. At the moment, the video from the **Webinar: "Sustainable Models for GLAMs" proposed by GLAMMONS, ReCharge and LibrarIN** of the project is available on LibrarIN YouTube channel (<https://youtu.be/bOKpLvYLLXc>).

Figure 16 shows the home page of LibrarIN YouTube channel. Up to date we have 26 views and 7 subscribers.

Figure 16: LibrarIN YouTube channel

3.3 Scientific Publications

During the first 18 months, LibrarIN research partners have published the following four articles in peer-reviewed journals while another one is under proofreading process.

- Gupta, V. and Gupta, C. (2023), "Transforming entrepreneurial research: leveraging library research services and technology innovations for rapid information discovery", *Online Information Review*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-04-2023-0156>
- Haug, N., Dan, S., & Mergel, I. (2023). Digitally-induced change in the public sector: a systematic review and research agenda. *Public Management Review*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2023.2234917>
- Gupta, V., Gupta, C., Swacha, J. and Rubalcaba, L. (2023), "Prototyping technology adoption among entrepreneurship and innovation libraries for rural health innovations", *Library Hi Tech*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-03-2023-0120>
- "Wertschöpfung und soziale Innovation für eine neue Generation von Bibliotheken in der EU: Neues EU-Horizon-2020-Projekt zu Bibliotheksinnovationen (LibrarIn)" *Bibliothek Forschung und Praxis*, vol. 47, no. 1, 2023, pp. 170-171. <https://doi.org/10.1515/bfp-2023-0018>

3.4 LibrarIN Blog posts

LibrarIN maintains a very active blog on its website, where project-related news is published, along with project events, other developments in the fields of social innovation, co-creation, and libraries and more. The blog has currently published 25 blog posts with the aim to disseminate project results and news, increase engagement, and drive additional traffic to LibrarIN website. As such, LibrarIN blog is one of the main channels for attracting new visitors to the website and disseminating project news and results.

Figure 17: Blog on the LibrarIN website

Figure 18: Example of blog post on LibrarIN blog

3.5 Attendance to conferences

An essential part of the dissemination activities is participating in national and international events such as conferences. The following list is an overview of presentations and participations of individual partners in the context of LibrarIN that have been reported up to now.

- **32nd Conference of the European Association for REsearch on SERvices (RESER 2022), 8-10 December 2022, Paris, France:** LibrarIN partners Professor Lars Fuglsang, from Department of Social Sciences and Business at Roskilde University, and Kirsi-Maria Hyytinen, Research team Leader (Future-proof Societies) and Senior scientist at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, were among the speakers of the round tables and had the opportunity to present the LibrarIN vision and approach.
- **Public libraries as future knowledge infrastructures: particular playgrounds or universal knowledge spaces?, TA23-Konferenz, 6 June 2023, Vienna, Austria:** LibrarIN partner Mrs. Dana Wasserbacher from Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH (AIT), held a presentation titled "Public libraries as future knowledge infrastructures." In the session, themed "Transformation of knowledge infrastructures," two other case studies on knowledge infrastructures, i.e. media and vision assessment, were presented alongside the forward-looking approach of the LibrarIN project. With approximately 100 participants from esteemed institutions, universities, media and public administrations, the conference as a whole, but also the presentation on libraries as future knowledge infrastructures, garnered positive feedback,

highlighting the importance of analysing libraries from a future-oriented perspective and reimagining them as heterotopic spaces.

Figure 19: Image from LibrarIN participation at the TA23-Konferenz

- **Congress of Novagob 2023, 7-8 November 2023, Madrid, Spain:** Professor and Innovation Coordinator Luis Rubalcaba from the University of Alcalá (UAH) presented the LibrarIN project at this congress. The University of Alcalá together with the City Council and the Community of Madrid were the co-organisers of the 10th Congress of the Novagob Foundation (#Novagob2023), which took place on 7th and 8th November 2023 in the Nave de Madrid. The opening session was attended by the Vice-Chancellor María Sarabia, together with other personalities including the Mayor of Madrid, José Luis Martínez Almeida. This congress has had more than 1,500 participants.

Figure 20: Images from LibrarIN participation at Congress of Novagob 2023

3.6 Workshops

3.6.1 LIBER 2023 - LibrarIN Pre-Conference Workshop

During the reporting period, LibrarIN project organised a pre-conference workshop titled **"Value Co-Creation and Social Innovation for a New Generation of European Libraries"** on July 5th, 2023, in Budapest, Hungary, in the framework of LIBER's Annual Conference 2023.

LibrarIN representatives Lars Fulgsang (RUC), Anthony Arundel (UM), Andrej Vrcon and Barbara van der Vaart (LIBER) shared the latest project updates and addressed around 30 librarians gathered for the occasion.

The workshop was divided into four moments. The first moment explained the project's aim: bringing innovation and collaboration within libraries. It was essential to clear out the jargon with professionals from the field.

The second moment was about the gaps the project is still trying to identify: it concerns the differences in vocabulary from one European country to another to address innovation and digital transformation in public and private libraries, but also the identification of already existing cases of innovation initiatives within libraries. Anthony Arundel (UM) outlined the upcoming survey on user-oriented innovations in libraries, including the types of questions it would contain. Attendees engaged in discussions to identify the best job levels to target for the survey, focusing on those with hands-on experience in managing such innovations. By gathering input from conference participants, UM aimed to ensure the survey reaches the most relevant audience, enhancing the quality of research insights.

After these exchanges, the librarians were invited to participate in an interactive exercise: split into three groups, they were tasked to draft a co-creative and innovative library project with the following criteria: new, useful and feasible. This was a very instructive session. It shows what innovation for librarians is and how it is articulated and made possible from within. The three propositions were about IA awareness, maker spaces and enabling innovative environments.

The workshop concluded with an introduction to the Stakeholder Representatives Panel. The Panel will allow 25 library stakeholders and more to be involved in the LibrarIN project. Library stakeholders are from various backgrounds and experiences: public libraries (national, municipal, community and libraries), directors and managers of international library organisations, academics and policymakers, and civil society representatives. They will create innovative library projects together in synergy with LibrarIN researchers, support validating concepts from the project, and later help disseminate the project's results and outcomes.

Following the workshop, two librarians applied to join the Panel.

Figure 21: Images from LibrarIN workshop at LIBER's Annual Conference 2023

The workshop programme and presentation can be found in Annex I: LIBER 2023 - LibrarIN Pre-Conference Workshop– Programme and Annex II: LIBER 2023 - LibrarIN Pre-Conference Workshop– Presentation respectively.

3.6.2 Online preparatory meeting with Stakeholder Panel

On September 11th, 2023, an online introductory meeting marked the initiation of the Stakeholder Panel's engagement. Serving as an orientation session, the meeting familiarized participants with the project and their fellow panel members. The primary objective was to prepare panel members for the first in-person Stakeholder Panel meeting (workshop) in Amsterdam. This meeting, attended by 26 panel members and 12 consortium members, provided a platform for active contributions to shaping the workshop's objectives and agenda, enhancing the benefits for both the project and the Stakeholder Panel.

The agenda for this meeting is available in Annex III: Online preparatory meeting with Stakeholder Panel – Agenda. A full report of the meeting is showcased in Deliverable "D5.1 Co-design and co-creation plan".

3.6.3 First in-person Stakeholder Panel meeting (full day workshop)

On October 6th, 2023, the first in-person Stakeholder Panel meeting unfolded in Vrije Universiteit in Amsterdam, Netherlands, as an active workshop. With a total of 42 participants, including 22 panel members and 20 consortium members, the workshop aimed to achieve several key objectives:

- Introduce Panel members and consortium partners to each other.
- Understand stakeholders' expectations and needs.
- Gather feedback on LibrarIN's project objectives and results.
- Explore future possibilities for interaction and cooperation within LibrarIN.

The workshop emerged as a dynamic and collaborative event, laying the groundwork for co-creation processes. It facilitated active engagement and discussions between researchers and stakeholders, resulting in valuable insights and suggestions for collaborative efforts. This meeting exemplified the commitment to fruitful collaboration within the LibrarIN project.

The agenda (see Annex IV: First in-person Stakeholder Panel meeting in Amsterdam - Agenda) was designed to facilitate engagement and networking, starting with an introduction to the project and brief stakeholder presentations. The workshop was focused on interactive activities such as a "speed dating" exercise to foster personal connections, slide presentations on key research topics, a poster session for interactive Q&A, and a World Café discussion in three groups on the research topics of Digital Transformation, Networks and Innovation Labs. The workshop culminated in a brainstorming session to shape future collaboration and was followed by an evaluation. A full report of the workshop is showcased in Deliverable "D5.1 Co-design and co-creation plan".

Figure 22: Photos from the First in-person Stakeholder Panel meeting in Amsterdam

3.7 Synergies at national or international levels for sharing knowledge

3.7.1 Horizon Europe Community Österreich - Deep Dives

LibrarIN partner Doris Schartinger from Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH (AIT) participated in a deep dive event on EU projects in the cultural heritage sector (<https://horizon-europe-community.at/page-4681>), invited and organised by the Austrian Research Foundation (FFG). This was a webinar taking place on November 21st, 2023 and lasted for two hours. LibrarIN was presented and followed by some Q&A around the project contents and their relation to the green, digital and innovative Cultural Heritage focus by the European Commission. Around 40 participants were present from academia and cultural heritage organisations. Three projects were (re-)presented (Time machine, LibrarIN, Kulturpool).

3.7.2 Cluster HERITAGE-01-02 projects

In order to ensure complementarities and in the interest of maximizing benefits, synergies and cooperation activities have been launched among the Cluster HERITAGE-01-02 projects, namely [GLAMMONS](#), [RECHARGE](#) and [LibrarIN](#). Following the 1st Cluster Meeting held online on March 30th 2023, the Cluster projects set up by the European Commission have maintained regular communications in order to explore synergies and detect possibilities for collaboration. Two online meetings among the three projects were held on October 10th and December 15th, 2023 respectively, where the projects discussed organising a joint dissemination event that would have an integrated approach with the possibility to discuss commonalities, share experiences and create real synergies. In addition, a Basecamp Group has been set up in order to facilitate communication among the cluster projects.

The outcome of these discussions between the three projects, was the organisation of the webinar titled *"Sustainable Models for GLAMs-New ways of participatory management and sustainable financing of cultural institutions"* on February 20th, 2024, from 13:00-15:00 CET. The webinar was a platform for GLAMMONS, ReCharge, and LibrarIN to share their unique visions and methodologies for enhancing participation in the cultural sphere. They delved into the importance of these methodologies, conducted needs assessments, and discussed capacity building, setting the stage for an enriching dialogue with attendees. The webinar was broadcasted on the GLAMMONS Facebook page. 209 participants registered for the event through the subscription form that was promoted prior to the event through the projects' social media accounts, while 99 persons attended the webinar.

Figure 23: Examples of posts in LibrarIN X/Twitter and LinkedIn - Webinar "Sustainable Models for GLAMs"

The webinar programme and communication material can be found in Annex V: Webinar: "Sustainable Models for GLAMs" – Programme and Annex VI: Webinar: "Sustainable Models for GLAMs" – Communication visuals respectively.

The recording of the webinar can be found on LibrarIN YouTube channel [here](#).

Figure 24: Video recording in LibrarIN YouTube channel - Webinar "Sustainable Models for GLAMs"

3.8 Partners Activities

During the first 18 months of the project LibrarIN partners have multiplied the visibility of the project, its activities and results via further web presence such as project pages and news on their websites, articles in their newsletters (e.g. the LIBER monthly newsletter), and sharing posts in institutional social media channels.

Figure 25: Example of AIT LinkedIn post

Figure 26: Example of LC LinkedIn post

Figure 27: Example of post in LIBER's X/Twitter

Figure 28: Example of LibrarIN article in LIBER INSIDER

Figure 29: Example of post in ATC's Facebook

4 Project Materials

This section provides an overview of the materials created for the promotion of the project.

4.1 Visual Identity and Logo

A strong visual identity has been created for LibrarIN in the beginning of the project, as showcased in Deliverable "D6.1 Dissemination, Communication & Sustainability Plan".

The logo was designed according to the project's theme on providing new avenues for participatory management and sustainable finance for European libraries as key cultural institutions. The logo is composed of three elements:

- A graphic representing books in an ablative depiction,
- The project's acronym is highlighted in bold characters,
- A coloured dot to stress the project's acronym pronunciation and add vividness.

Figure 30: LibrarIN Logo

Figure 31: LibrarIN logo - versions adapting to different backgrounds

The logo or the icon version of it (Figure 32), is used in all communication materials, to personalise them and allow for the visual identity and the LibrarIN brand to become well established and well-known. The display of EU funding information is also a concern in all communication and dissemination materials.

Figure 32: LibrarIN icon

A complete LibrarIN brand guide featuring the logo and its use, the colour scheme, typography, imagery, brand elements etc. was developed and shared with all consortium partners. It is also available for download on the project’s website at the link [here](#).

4.2 Project PPT presentation

LibrarIN presentation is part of the project’s tools to support dissemination efforts and has been designed to be used by all the partners when they present the project to various events.

Figure 33: LibrarIN ppt presentation

4.3 Visuals

Several visuals have been prepared to present the project on social media using the LibrarIN visual identity. The project logo or icon is present in every visual to maintain coherency throughout all communication efforts.

Figure 34: LibrarIN visuals – example

4.4 Project brochure

The objective of the project brochure is to give an overview of the project, its objectives, results, and expected impact, with the aim to raise the awareness around and visibility of the project and to be distributed at key events and conferences by the project partners. Figure 35 below presents the project’s brochure.

Objectives

LibrarIN will discover, analyse and provide managerial and policy recommendations for transformative strategies that integrate the co-creation of value in public libraries.

- Provide a comprehensive and holistic theoretical framework
- Measure and monitor transformative innovation in public libraries
- Focus on three areas of transformation within public service co-creation in libraries
- Generate sustainable impact in library policy and practice
- Set up an online tracker system for the benchmarking of library value co-creation
- Exploit the achievements of LibrarIN through a sustainable research and innovation lighthouse

Targeted Results

Theoretical framework

To understand the process of value co-creation in libraries' service delivery, developing and operationalising existing approaches on knowledge creation, service delivery, and social innovation.

New evidence and metrics

For library transformation and existing or ongoing efforts to develop innovative public services in ways that enable the co-creation of value.

Policy Recommendations & Tools

For implementing new ideas and scaling up best-practices that use value co-creation to unlock social assets, including indicators for monitoring and evaluating existing initiatives.

Expected Impact

LibrarIN aims to modernise libraries. It will deliver sustainable and measurable results that will push the boundaries of current scientific knowledge and policy practices. The result? Libraries can "re-position" themselves at the core of cultural and socioeconomic activity in the neighbourhoods, cities and regions where they operate. The project will have both scientific and policy-related impacts.

Scientific Impact

- Establish the foundations of a new, comprehensive and holistic paradigm for understanding the transformation of libraries. This will be viewed from a co-creation perspective that integrates public service logic (PSL) in a new model of public governance (NPG) and multi-agent frameworks.
- Enrich theories of innovation in services in general, considering the library services and demand and user-driven innovation that underlie demand-driven innovation policies.
- Provide new metrics and empirical evidence for value co-creation in public administration through the LibrarIN survey on transformative innovation in libraries. Implications for further innovation surveys and an impact on future OECD work on public sector innovation can also be expected.

Policy Impact

- Support library transformation through incentives that will help overcome cultural resistance to innovation and change.
- Encourage broader adoption of co-creation practices to enable cost savings, better services, increased public trust and innovation.
- Ensure that the research findings will reach policymakers and practitioners at different institutional levels throughout Europe.
- Enhance thought leadership, by translating the project's findings into actionable policy recommendations that will reach policymakers and practitioners at different institutional levels throughout Europe.
- Deliver a data-driven tracking system for allowing immediate comparison and benchmarking of the extent to which libraries are implementing collaborative initiatives in line with recommendations.
- Build the foundation for a sustainable research and innovation lighthouse, that will sustain on the achievements of the project in the years to come.

Figure 35: LibrarIN Brochure

4.5 Project Poster

LibrarIN has produced a poster in A0 format that reflects the scope of the project. The poster presents in brief the aims of the project, as well as contact information for further communication, partners' logos, LibrarIN web-based channels and the EU logo with reference to the project's funding framework.

By being both a printed and electronic poster, the LibrarIN poster enables the consortium partners to use it at dissemination events and workshops (Print-On-The-Go), where project results and activities are presented, and to disseminate it through their respective websites.

Figure 36: LibrarIN Poster

4.6 Press release

A first press release was created in English to communicate the kick-off of the project and has been shared to all project partners for further dissemination through their networks and organisations.

Figure 37: Examples of LibrarIN 1st Press Release in partners' websites

More press releases are under way, as the research and policy work packages will gradually deliver their scientific results and policy recommendations respectively.

4.7 Newsletter

The LibrarIN team has exploited the Mailchimp marketing platform to create and send the inaugural edition of the LibrarIN newsletter on December 6th, 2023. The newsletter, highlighting the accomplishments of the project's first year, was sent via email to 49 subscribers. It was also shared through LibrarIN online channels and promoted through partners online media channels, reaching out to more than 4.000 subscribers through consortium network members. At this stage, the newsletter counts 92 subscribers.

Subscribe Past Issues Translate RSS

Welcome to the first LibrarIN newsletter

Dear reader,

We are delighted to share with you the inaugural edition of the LibrarIN newsletter!

[LibrarIN](#) is a 36-month Horizon Europe project funded by the European Union aspiring to provide new avenues for participatory management and sustainable financing for European libraries – pivotal cultural institutions in our society. [Our mission](#) encompasses exploring how libraries can evolve, introducing novel functions, services, and engagement strategies with the individuals, organisations, and communities they serve. This journey demands social innovation founded on public value co-creation and a demand-driven design of library services.

Within this newsletter, you will find updates and insights into [the LibrarIN Stakeholder Panel](#), which was inaugurated in March 2023. The panel brings together passionate individuals committed to innovating within the realm of libraries. Furthermore, we share highlights from [LibrarIN's Third General Assembly](#) in Amsterdam, a significant milestone where we assessed our progress after nearly a year of intensive activities and explored the next steps. We are pleased to introduce you to the newly established [LibrarIN community](#) on Zenodo and to share the latest project deliverables.

As we reflect on the accomplishments of our first year, we eagerly anticipate the challenges and achievements that Year 2 of LibrarIN will bring. The journey ahead promises further exploration, innovation, and impactful outcomes, and we are delighted to have you with us in this endeavour.

Stay tuned for more updates and insights in the coming months. Your interest in our work is genuinely appreciated.

Thank you for being part of our community! Enjoy the reading!

The LibrarIN Team

The LibrarIN Stakeholder Panel: A Collaboration for Innovative Libraries

In March, following an open call, LibrarIN launched a Stakeholder Panel. As the project seeks to bring innovation in the context of libraries, who else than librarians to effect such changes? Their diverse expertise is expected to feed the LibrarIN project: from this collaboration new insights will emerge to redefine libraries.

[Read more](#)

Figure 38: 1st LibrarIN Newsletter

5 Dissemination & Communication Impact assessment

This section assesses the impact of the performed dissemination and communication activities by comparing their quantitative indicators against the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as set in Deliverable "D6.1 Dissemination, Communication & Sustainability Plan". Based on the KPIs and their description in D6.1, and considering the dissemination and communication activities so far, the following table (Table 4) indicates of how effective these activities were during the first 18 months of the project. It is important to note that most key dissemination and communication activities are still in progress, as expected in M18 (marked with an orange status) and only a few have been achieved so far (marked with a green status). We will continue tracking the KPIs to ensure that all key dissemination and communication activities will be achieved by the end of Y3.

Table 4: LibrarIN Dissemination and Communication KPIs tracking for M1-M18

Indicator	KPIs Y1-Y3	KPIs M1-M18	Status
Project Website	≥1.000 accesses annually, ≥100 downloads	2.691 users 536 downloads	Orange
Social Media	≥100 Posts yearly, ≥300 Followers (X/Twitter: 60 posts yearly, and a total of 200 followers; LinkedIn: 40 posts yearly, and a total of 100 followers)	X/Twitter: 262 posts with retweets, 105 followers	Orange
		LinkedIn: 80 posts with retweets, 190 followers	Orange
Brochure	≥1.000 hard copies distributed in ≥ 10 events, ≥100 downloads	100 hard copies distributed in 2 events	Orange
		179 downloads	Green
Newsletters	≥3 newsletters (one newsletter yearly)	1	Orange
Video	≥1 video	1 video from cluster webinar available in YouTube	Orange
Traditional media	≥ 2 media appearances	0	Orange
Scientific publications	≥20 open-access publications; ≥20 Conference publications; ≥1 selected paper/issue in international journal	5	Orange

Indicator	KPIs Y1-Y3	KPIs M1-M18	Status
Magazine publications and blogs	≥5 publications and 10 blog posts	25	
Attendance to conferences	10 conferences attended, 100 visitors	3	
Conference organisation	1 conference organised	0	
Workshops	Organise at least 5 workshops with stakeholders	3	
Synergies at national or international levels for sharing knowledge	≥ 3 projects	4	
Policy Events	4 policy events	0	

6 Future Plans

The second half of the project will be focused more on disseminating and communicating the project’s research results and policy implications to the different target audiences, producing results-oriented communication material, but also on connecting with audiences, relevant communities, and research projects across Europe for input and collaboration.

We will keep participating in events, conferences, and workshops and will continuously seek opportunities to promote LibrarIN through publications. Moreover, we plan to strengthen our collaboration with LibrarIN’s stakeholder panel through the organization of more stakeholder meetings and the frequent communication we already have with them through official and unofficial channels.

During the second half of the project, we will also focus on publishing and disseminating LibrarIN’s policy briefs and organizing the accompanying policy events to involve the European community of policy making and public administration as much as possible at both national and European levels.

6.1 Indicative dissemination events

Table 5 below presents some indicative venues (events, conferences) that have already been identified as useful for LibrarIN dissemination within the 2nd half of the project (May 2024 – October 2025).

Table 5: Indicative dissemination events for M19-M36

Title of event	Place	Date	Topics	Partner
ERSA- Regional sciences for peace and sustainable development	Portugal- Azores	26-30 August 2024	Digital geographies-The future of libraires	ULILLE
ISIRC Conference	Bern, Switzerland	2-4 September, 2024	Libraries and social innovation ecosystems	AIT
RESER conference	Helsinki, Finland	31 October – 2 November, 2024	Co-creating sustainable solutions for Future-proof Societies	RUC
L'entrée de l'Intelligence Artificielle dans les espaces bibliothéconomiques et documentaires: entre imaginaires et pratiques engagées	France	6 November 2024	AI and Libraries	ULILLE
LIBER 2025 Annual Conference	TBD	TBD	Library research	UM
EBLIDA 2025 Conference	TBD	TBD- April 2025?	TBD	TBD

Title of event	Place	Date	Topics	Partner
WLIC 2025 (IFLA world congress)	TBD	TBD - August 2025?	TBD	TBD

6.2 Indicative scientific journals

Table 6 presents a list of scientific journals/books that will be targeted to maximize the impact of the scientific work to the target communities within the 2nd half of the project (May 2024 – October 2025).

Table 6: List of indicative scientific journals/books

Journal Name	URL	Partner
Research Policy	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/research-policy	UKON, RUC
Government Information Quarterly	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/government-information-quarterly	UKON
International Journal of Information Management	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-information-management	UKON
Journal of Service Research	https://journals.sagepub.com/home/jsr	RUC
InterCDI	https://www.intercdi.org/	ULILLE
Library & Information Science Research	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/library-and-information-science-research	UM
Journal of Library Administration	https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/wjla20	UM
Library Management	https://www.emeraldgroupublishing.com/journal/lm	UM
The Library Quarterly	https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/loi/lq	UM
Public Library Quarterly	https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/wp1q20	UM
Cybergeog-European journal of geography	https://submissions.cybergeog.org/index.php/cybergeog/about	ULILLE
Netcom-Networks and communication studies	https://journals.openedition.org/netcom/?lang=en	ULILLE
Innovations-Journal of economics and management of innovation	https://riifr.univ-littoral.fr/rii/icei-2/	ULILLE
Cahiers de géographie du Québec (Laval University)	https://revues.ulaval.ca/ojs/index.php/cahiers-geographie-quebec	ULILLE
Cities-International Journal of urban policy and planning	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/cities	ULILLE
Library HiTech	https://www.emeraldgroupublishing.com/journal/lht	UAH
The Journal of Academic Librarianship	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/the-journal-of-academic-librarianship	UAH

7 Conclusions

This deliverable, D6.2 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities v1.0, is part of WP6 “Dissemination, Communication and Sustainability” and has provided information regarding the project’s dissemination and communication activities during the first 18 months of the project (November 2022 - April 2024). An overview of the related communication tools and communication/dissemination activities used to disseminate the project’s results were presented.

In general words, after the project's first half, we can conclude that our dissemination efforts are on track. Dissemination and communication at the project level are running on a daily basis, and the progress made by the consortium is visible, and partners are actively participating. Through monitoring the set dissemination and communication KPIs we can keep track of the progress and identify quickly which activities need more attention and which have surpassed the objectives.

The dissemination and communication activities focused on reaching representatives from all the different target audiences through: i) publications to journals, ii) presentations to conferences and events, iii) organisation of workshops, and iv) distribution of communication material within the consortium’s network.

More specifically, articles have been published in European journals and in journals with a worldwide reach. The number of scientific publications for the first half of the project could be seen as relatively low. Still the number reflects the fact that research results are generated later on in the course of the project, combined with the fact that the process for publishing a paper in a peer-reviewed journal is lengthy and time-consuming. On the other hand, partners have participated in several national and international conferences, disseminating the project’s results mainly to the scientific and libraries community.

Finally, LibrarIN has established – through its stakeholders’ panel – a diverse group of experts who are passionate about innovation in libraries and bring a wealth of expertise in innovation and co-creation. The stakeholder panel can provide valuable feedback on LibrarIN’s research results and their transformation to policy recommendations.

8 Annexes

8.1 Annex I: LIBER 2023 - LibrarIN Pre-Conference Workshop– Programme

Pre-Conference Workshop 10
“Value Co-Creation and Social Innovation for a New Generation of European Libraries”

Wednesday, 5 July 2023
9h00-12h00
Venue: [Central European University \(CEU\) Room 106](#)
1054 Budapest, Nádor u.15

The workshop goals are:

- 1. To present the LibrarIN Horizon Europe project** key terms will be explained and defined, and the aims of the project elaborated. The role of research librarians in the process of social innovations and the value co-creation of library services will be outlined.
- 2. Interactive session – value co-creation and innovation in your library**
The interactive session is to uncover the power of value co-creation in library service delivery and to assess the various models of knowledge transformation in libraries. The interactive session will give participants the opportunity to share their unique experiences with value co-creation and social innovation in libraries. Participants will benefit from sharing their experiences of value co-creation and social innovation in libraries, and workshop ideas that they can put into practice at their own institutions (e.g. the concept of living labs, digital services for value co-creation and methods of encouraging social entrepreneurship within libraries). The LibrarIN project gains a snapshot into existing value-cocreation practices in LIBER libraries and the attitude to such activities amongst the research community.

Workshop contact: Andrej Vrčon
Head of International Projects, LIBER
Email: andrej.vrcon@libereurope.org

Programme

1.	Opening remarks by Andrej Vrčon and Barbara van der Vaart, LIBER	9h00-9h05
2.	Managing Employee and User Engagement in Library Innovation <i>Presentation of innovation, co-creation, value co-creation, and business model innovation concepts.</i> Speaker: Lars Fuglsang (Roskilde University)	9h05-9h30 25 min presentation
3.	User Involvement in Innovation <i>Surveying user involvement in innovation in EU research and public libraries.</i> Speaker: Anthony Arundel (UNU-MERIT, Maastricht University)	9h30-10h00 30 min presentation
4.	Interactive session: Cocreating Innovation with Users <i>The division into groups, collaborative work.</i> Moderated by: Lars Fuglsang, Anthony Arundel, Barbara Van der Vaart, Andrej Vrčon	10h00-10h30 30 min collaborative work
Coffee break (30 minutes)		10h30-11h00
5.	Interactive session: Cocreating Innovation with Users <i>Continuation of collaborative work and presentation of work in the groups</i> Moderated by: Lars Fuglsang, Anthony Arundel, Barbara Van der Vaart, Andrej Vrčon	11h00-11h40 40 min collaborative work
6.	LibrarIN Stakeholder Representatives Panel <i>Composition, role, and engagement with the project</i> Speaker: Barbara Van der Vaart	11h40-11h55 15 min presentation
7.	Wrap up by Lars Fuglsang, Anthony Arundel	11h55-12h00

Biography of Speakers

Lars Fuglsang	Lars Fuglsang is Professor at Roskilde University. His main research interest is how institutional and organisational frameworks are created to deal with the impact of innovation, technology and other forms of change on business and society. His current research is focusing on a practice based understanding of the innovation process. He has published his work in journals such as Public Management Review , Research Policy, Journal of Rural Studies , European Urban and Regional Studies, Tourism Management, Annals of Tourism Research, and Technological Forecasting and Social Change
Anthony Arundel	Anthony Arundel is a Professorial Fellow at UNU-MERIT, a joint research institute of the United Nations University and the University of Maastricht in the Netherlands. He is an expert in the design, implementation, and analysis of innovation surveys in both the business and public sectors, with relevant articles on public sector innovation published in the Australian Journal of Public Administration, Public Management Review, Research Policy, and Structural Change and Economic Dynamics.
Barbara Van der Vaart	Barbara van der Vaart joined LIBER as a Community Engagement and Training Officer as of August 2022. In this role, she works on international projects and aims to engage LIBER's network with high-quality and impactful workshops and training sessions. Barbara has a background in international project management and worked as a project coordinator and policy officer in academic research projects and governmental and international organisations. Before joining LIBER, she worked on two ERC Grant projects at Delft University and Leiden University. She obtained an MSc degree in Cultural Anthropology at Utrecht University, where she also studied Child and Adolescent Psychology.
Andrej Vrčon	Andrej Vrčon is the Head of International Projects at the LIBER office, coordinating the organisation's participation in eight EU Horizon-funded projects. He has extensive expertise in EU project management, regional economic development, project evaluations, fundraising and democracy development. As a project coordinator and manager, he worked for the Slovenian government, Think Thank Centre for European Perspective and the EU public-private partnership Climate-KIC. Andrej obtained PhD in the History of Europe and the Mediterranean from the University of Primorska, Koper, Slovenia, and an MA in European Public Policy from the University of Sussex. His research interest lies in the History of European Integrations.

8.2 Annex II: LIBER 2023 - LibrarIN Pre-Conference Workshop– Presentation

Value Co-Creation and Social Innovation for a New Generation of European Libraries

Lars Fuglsang, Anthony Arundel, Andrej Vrčon, Barbara van der Vaart

LIBER Annual Conference, July 4th, 2023
Budapest, Hungary

This project is funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101061516. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by the European Union

What is LibrarIN?

- ✓ LibrarIN is striving to empower European libraries as important cultural institutions through **participatory management and long-term funding**.
- ✓ It will look at how libraries might **expand their roles, services, and involvement** with the people, organisations, and communities they serve.
- ✓ By collaborating to create **public value through social innovation**, libraries can ensure they are providing the most relevant and beneficial services to their communities.

Outcomes

The LibrarIN value co-creation concept aims to produce three outcomes

Theoretical framework

Understand the process of value co-creation in libraries' service delivery, developing and operationalising existing approaches on knowledge creation, service delivery, and social innovation.

New evidence and metrics

For library transformation and existent and ongoing efforts to develop innovative public services in ways that enable the co-creation of value.

Policy Recommendations & Tools

For implementing new ideas and scaling up best-practices that use value-co-creation to unlock social assets. Indicators for monitoring and evaluating existing initiatives to support public service transformation.

Partners

 Roskilde University				
 AIT Austrian Institute of Technology				

Innovation: what it is

- Developing new ideas and implementing these ideas in practice.
- Innovations must represent step-changes to count as innovations.
- Innovation is not the same as improvement.
- Public innovation must offer value for individuals and society.
- Public value = what the public values and what adds value to the public sphere (Bennington, 2011)

Different processes of innovation

Toivonen and Tuominen 2009

Service innovation processes

- R&D departments and laboratories are very rarely involved
- Service innovation is often less radical and groundbreaking than manufacturing
- They are very practice-based and market-based and often grounded in users' perceived problems.
- The path from conceiving an idea to creating value for users is, thus, shorter than that for developing and introducing goods

Employee innovation roles

- (1) Idea provider
- (2) Intrapreneur/entrepreneur
- (3) Bricoleur
- (4) Developer
- (5) Coordinator
- (6) Sponsor
- (7) Producer
- (8) Learner

Why involve users?

- "... understanding customer needs and requirements constitutes an essential foundation for sustained competitiveness through innovative new products and services"
- "in several industries, the vast majority of innovations have emanated from lead users' ideas"

(Magnussen et al. 2003)

- Create innovations that are relevant for users -> bigger chance of success

Relating use information for service innovation

- The correspondent: Users are in a real life use situation (method e.g. observation of user behaviour)
- The reflective practitioner: Users have been or are going to be in a real life use situation (method e.g. user surveys, or focus and discussion groups)
- The tester: Users are in a simulated use situation (method e.g. prototype test)
- The dreamer: Users imagine to be in a use situation (method e.g. interview "what would you do if..." , or in focus and discussion groups)

Edvardsson et al. 2012

Why not involve users?

- Innovative ideas rarely arise from customers
- Perception is limited to what consumers can currently relate to.
- Consumers' ability to express and verbalize their needs is limited
- They do not know what is technologically feasible – lack technological knowledge
- Needs expressed by consumers may well have changed by the time the new product is developed and ready.
- Lack imagination (reject later successes).
- Or users do come up with imaginative ideas, however, they are often less feasible (Trischer 2018)
- Limits exploration

Collaborative innovation and sustainable innovation

- Libraries as living labs: Living labs are user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings (<https://enoll.org/about-us>).
- Collaborative innovation: Based on 'shared intentions' among multiple stakeholders working

Three types of living labs scenarios

Three degrees of library innovation through living labs

- System maintenance (same for more)
- System extension (more for same – and more)
- System transformation (becoming different).

Hansen et al. 2022

Questions

- In your experience, where do innovations come from in the library sector (patrons, staff, managers, government)?
- Are there examples of system transformations innovation emerging from multiple stakeholders working together with shared intentions?
- What innovation ideas do you work on?

Due to case studies and research on trends, we know that many libraries have been innovating by introducing new or improved processes (often digitalization) and new or improved services

But there is a lot we don't know:

- How do libraries innovate?
- How do managers decide on the **intensity** of user involvement in innovation?
- What combination of factors lead to good innovation outcomes?
- What methods for measuring outcomes are useful?

**Multiple solutions:
some methods for
innovating may be
less efficient, but
they might still
produce a usable
innovation**

What types of outcomes are relevant?

What types of user
involvement contribute to
better outcomes?

How can evaluation
practices be designed to
produce better outcomes?

Data for multiple library innovations from different types of libraries can help in answering these questions

Benchmarking metrics
Data analysis

We searched for existing innovation data for multiple libraries (research & public), but little available

Innovation questionnaires build on previous research – but very few innovation surveys for libraries (sample > 30)

Author	Country	Sample size	Topics covered
Potnis et al, 2020	US	108 librarians	Importance of innovations, top 3 challenges, solutions
Cruz et al, 2020	Brazil	107 librarians	Front line employee and user involvement in service innovation, innovation performance
Arundel et al, 2016	Australia	79 library managers	User involvement, innovation inputs and outcomes, management support, 'pro-innovation' culture
Jantz, 2017	US	50 libraries	Decisions to adopt innovations, factors leading to incremental versus radical innovations

- More surveys on adoption of new technologies, but very few other questions.
- Some public sector innovation surveys (Denmark, Sweden), no results for libraries.

LibrarIN survey of European libraries

- Cover research and public libraries
- Sample of approximately 2000 libraries
- Online and printed versions
- Require approximately 15 minutes to answer
- Focus on how innovations developed, including input from stakeholders and user involvement in developing innovations.

**Three questions
for you about our
planned LibrarIN
survey**
(I am hoping for a
discussion)

Who within a library makes decisions about innovation?

Who has hands-on experience with developing innovations?

If there are multiple libraries within a system, how much decision-making power does each library have?

Are you aware of existing data, from surveys or other sources, of innovation in libraries?

If innovation isn't covered in surveys that you know about, any ideas why not?

Most importantly:

**What questions
would be of interest
to you – what would
you like to know
about innovation in
libraries?**

Thank you!

a.arundel@maastrichtuniversity.nl

Envision a co-creative, innovative library project with the following criteria: **New, Useful and Feasible (NUF).**

This project could be (but does not have to be) in the field of:

- Digital transformation, ICT
- Social entrepreneurship, public-private networks, social innovation
- Living labs, maker spaces

Take the following aspects into account:

- What is the scope of the project? Which public/user group would you like to target?
- How will you involve users? (i.e., do you interact directly with users? Will you use surveys?)
- Will the project have top-down or a bottom-up approach?
- What is the public value of your project?

LibrarIN

Stakeholder Representatives Panel:

Composition, role and engagement with the project

Barbara van der Vaart (LIBER Office)

LIBER Annual Conference , 4-6 July 2023
Budapest, Hungary

The LibrarIN project has received funding from EU HORIZON-CL2-2021-HERITAGE-01-02. Funded by the European Union

LibrarIN's Stakeholder Representatives Panel

- What is the Stakeholder Representatives Panel?
- How to become a member of the Panel?
- Be involved in the project or stay in touch?

1. Introduction to the Stakeholder Representatives Panel

25+ Library stakeholders will be involved in LibrarIN's activities as permanent members of the Panel:

- Create innovative library projects together in synergy with LibrarIN
- Validation of concepts
- Partners in the dissemination of results and outcomes

2.1 Composition of the Panel

A panel of **public service libraries and other relevant stakeholders**, with the following representation:

1. Stakeholder categories:
 - a. Public libraries: national, municipal, community/special libraries and academic libraries
 - b. Directors/managers of international library organisations
 - c. Academics
 - d. Policy makers
 - e. Civil society representatives
2. Geographical coverage in European countries:
EEA and EFTA countries, plus UK and Ukraine

2.2 Selection criteria

Library managers were selected based on two criteria:

1. **Experience** in public value co-creation and demand-driven design of library projects, especially when this connects to one or more of the following topics:
 1. Digital transformation and ICT
 2. Social entrepreneurship, public-private networks and social innovation
 3. Living labs for co-creation and co-innovation
2. **Motivation:**
 1. To be actively involved in the pursuing of projects in their libraries, and
 2. To use the project's toolkit, outcomes and recommendations in their projects

3 Current status of the Panel

- A panel of 29 members
- Additional panel members can be included (by invitation/recommendation)
 - Including librarians from a list of "Excellent" European municipal libraries

3.1 Composition of the Panel: introducing library representatives

Academic libraries

- Barcelona, Budapest, Constanz, Debrecen, Kyiv, Malmö, Prague, Ruse, Waterford

National Libraries

- Germany, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Spain

Municipal Libraries

- Järfälla, Lardero, La Rioja, Paderborn, Vienna

Community/special libraries

- C3 Library for International Development – NGO library, Vienna
- La Petite Bibliotheque Ronde-children’s library, Clamart (France)

3.2 Composition of the Panel: introducing other stakeholders

Academics - Hochschule der Medien (Stuttgart), Lorraine University

Policy Makers - Municipalities of Copenhagen and Oeiras (Portugal)

NGOs / Civil Society - Readers Association Copenhagen, C3 NGO Library Vienna

International Library Organisations:

4 Roles and engagements of the Panel

Stakeholder panel representative meetings (in-person and online)

The Panel will share their experiences and expertise, and will *develop library projects* with the project's researchers and other stakeholders (e.g. users, policy-makers), using of *design thinking techniques*

- The panel will have the benefit of access to:
 - Expertise being developed within the LibrarIN project
 - Cooperation with project's researchers in innovation projects in their libraries
 - Networking with fellow experts on innovation and value co-creation

- Invitation to participate in LibrarIN's final conference

The panel will have an *advisory and facilitating role* in the LibrarIN Project:

Feedback on LibrarIN's research activities:

- Feedback on the project developments and results
- Identification of best examples of innovation in libraries
- Participation in validation workshops

Take part in value co-creation activities:

- Co-creation of library initiatives by pursuing their own pilots in their home institutions
- Opportunity to work with LibrarIN's researchers in case studies work in their own libraries
- Participation in co-creation sessions (online), presenting their own existing projects
- Help identify LibrarIN's added value for existing projects/pilots, report on possible future benefits

Dissemination of LibrarIN's results

- Participation in LibrarIN's dissemination events
- Dissemination of LibrarIN results and initiatives in their own networks

5 Panel Meetings: tentative schedule

- **First Introductory Panel meeting (online), 11 September 2023**
 - Introduction of the LibrarIN Project and the panel members
 - Interactive session with researchers of the project
- **Second meeting (in-person, The Hague, 6 October 2023)**
 - Meeting with the consortium members ins a full day workshop
- **Follow up meetings**
 - Around every 6 months
 - Coinciding with or around time of LibrarIN's General Assembly meetings
 - In person or online

6 Let's stay in touch!

LibrarIN's Stakeholder Representatives Panel:

- Admission is now upon invitation only, but...
- Please express your interest to us. 😊

Projects in your library:

- Would you like to interact with us on current or future projects in your library?
 - ✓ Our researchers are happy to discuss your projects and share their ideas with you...
 - ✓ Your library could cooperate with LibrarIN in *use case studies*.

Follow us:

- Check <https://librarin.eu/> and subscribe to our newsletter
- Follow us on Twitter, LinkedIN and YouTube

8.3 Annex III: Online preparatory meeting with Stakeholder Panel – Agenda

Time	Duration	Subject	Presenter
15:00-15:15	15'	Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of LibrarIN and the consortium • Introduction to today's meeting: 	Lars Fuglsang Roskilde University
15:15-15:45	30'	Ice Breaker One Breath-introductions by the Panel members to get to know each other	Dana Wasserbacher Austrian Institute of technology
15:45 – 15:55	10'	Role and involvement of the Stakeholder Representatives Panel in LibrarIN	Barbara van der Vaart LIBER
15:55-16:20	25'	Contributions of stakeholders Share your ideas with us for creating a successful meeting in Amsterdam!	Ines Mergel University of Konstanz
16:20-16:25	5'	Outlook What to expect in Amsterdam and how to prepare for the plenary meeting?	Ines Mergel University of Konstanz
16:25-16:30	5'	Welcome to Amsterdam Some words on your visit to Amsterdam and VU University	Martine Pronk LIBER

8.4 Annex IV: First in-person Stakeholder Panel meeting in Amsterdam - Agenda

Time	Duration	Subject	Presenter
09:30 – 10:00	30'	Arrival of Participants (<i>coffee and tea</i>)	
10:00-10:15	15'	Welcome Meeting objectives, organization, and agenda Introduction to the project	Anna Triantafillou (ATC)
10:15 – 11:25	70'	Introduction and presentation of the Stakeholder panel members Short 2-minute presentation of each stakeholder	Luis Rubalcaba (UAH)
11:25 –11:40	15'	Coffee Break	
11:40-12:10	30'	Speed dating Forming personal connections in a more private setting through short conversations (3 minutes)	Elena Silvestrini (LC) and Dana Wasserbacher (AIT)
12:10 – 13:10	60'	Presentations (plenary session, 30 minutes) Objective: getting to know the project work and providing possibilities to ask questions 5-minute slide presentations on: Conceptual Framework, Digital Transformation, Networks, Innovation Labs, Survey, Use cases Poster Session (30 minutes) Q&A's in a casual walk-around-setting with 6 posters and presenters at each poster. Participants can freely choose where to go and where to ask questions.	Presenters: Luis Rubalcaba (UAH), Ines Mergel and Giulia Maragno (UKON), Benoit Desmarchelier and Faiz Gallouj (ULILLE), Lars Fuglsang (RUC), Anthony Arundel (UM), Alberto Peralta (UAH)
13:10– 14:10	60'	Lunch break	
14:10 – 15:10	60'	World Café Three topics will be discussed in three rounds à 15 minutes at six tables hosted by the presenters of the previous session: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital Transformation (Ines and Giulia) - Networks (Benoit and Faiz) - Innovation Labs (Lars) 	Table Hosts: Ines Mergel and Giulia Maragno (UKON), Benoit Desmarchelier and Faiz Gallouj (ULILLE), Lars Fuglsang (RUC)
15:10– 15:40	30'	Share back and wrap up of the World Café Table hosts report the discussion results on each of the three topics back in plenary	Table Hosts (of the previous session)
15:40-16:10	30'	Exploring expectations and future possibilities Objective: digest the input from today and explore future possibilities for collaboration and interaction of the Stakeholder panel and project consortium	Dana Wasserbacher (AIT) and Elena Silvestrini (LC)
16:10– 16:15	5'	Next meeting, next steps and closing of the meeting Evaluation of the event	Anna Triantafillou (ATC)

8.5 Annex V: Webinar: "Sustainable Models for GLAMs" – Programme

WEBINAR PROGRAM
Tuesday 20 February: Sustainable models for GLAMs

13.00-13.05 Welcome and introduction by Hinano Spreafico, European Commission, and the moderator, Ares Kalandides, GLAMMONS

13.05-13.15 GLAMMONS: Resilient, sustainable, and participatory practices: Towards the GLAMs of the commons by Vasilis Avdikos, GLAMMONS

13.15-13.25 RECHARGE: Resilient European Cultural Heritage as Resource for Growth and Engagement by Trilce Navarrete, RECHARGE

13.25-13.35 LibrarIN: Value co-creation and social innovation for a new generation of European libraries by Luis Rubalcaba and Andrej Vrčon, LibrarIN

Open discussion

13.35-14.00 The multiple financial channels of GLAMs, chaired by Janet Merkel (TUB)

14.00-14.25 Understanding and Fostering Participation in Cultural Heritage, chaired by Maja Drabczyk (Centrum Cyfrowe) with Una Hussey (The Hunt Museum), RECHARGE Living Labs and Kelly Hazejager (Sound & Vision), RECHARGE Playbook

14.25-14.50 Innovation in libraries and libraries as living labs, chaired by Lars Fuglsang and Luis Rubalcaba, LibrarIN

14.50-15.00 Wrap-up and closing of the event by Ares Kalandides

Funded by the European Union

RECHARGE Resilient European Cultural Heritage As Resource for Growth & Engagement

LibrarIN

GLAMMONS

8.6 Annex VI: Webinar: "Sustainable Models for GLAMs" – Communication visuals

**ONLINE
EVENT**

Sustainable models for GLAMs
New ways of participatory management and sustainable financing of cultural institutions
20.02.2024, 13:00-15:00 CET

Funded by the European Union

LibrarIN

RECHARGE Resilient European Cultural Heritage As Resource for Growth & Engagement

GLAMMONS

**ONLINE
EVENT**

Sustainable models for GLAMs
New ways of participatory management and sustainable financing of cultural institutions
20.02.2024, 13:00-15:00 CET

Funded by the European Union

LibrarIN

RECHARGE Resilient European Cultural Heritage As Resource for Growth & Engagement

GLAMMONS